

Recommended citation: Mesutoglu, C., Stollman, S., & Lopez Arteaga, I. (2021). Upscaling a challenge-based and modular education concept (CMODE-up). In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 1478-1483). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14651539.

UPSCALING A CHALLENGE-BASED AND MODULAR EDUCATION CONCEPT (CMODE-UP)

C Mesutoğlu¹

Eindhoven University of Technology
Eindhoven, the Netherlands

SHM Stollman

Eindhoven University of Technology
Eindhoven, the Netherlands

I Lopez Arteaga

Eindhoven University of Technology
Eindhoven, the Netherlands

Conference Key Areas: *Challenge based education, Methods, formats and essential elements for online/blended learning*

Keywords: *Challenge-based learning, Modular education, Systematic literature review, Instructional design framework*

ABSTRACT

In 2019, a course at a Dutch University of Technology was redesigned towards challenge-based and modular education. The course was received positively by students and their learning outcomes (grades and engagement) increased compared to previous years. This redesign was quite intensive, and case-specific. It did not deliver a specific set of design principles that can easily be used to redesign other courses within the university or even other universities. Therefore, a follow-up project was started, that aims to deliver a framework to scale-up the course redesign tested in the previous study (CMODE; Challenge-based Modular On-demand Digital Education). This framework will be designed using practical principles and will be evidence-informed. The project consists of three stages: (1) informal interviews with key actors at our university, experienced in studying and/or designing modular instruction, a systematic literature review on challenge-based education and modular instruction; (2) a test of the design principles that were developed using the interviews and literature review; and (3) a test of the CMODE-up framework that was built on the results from the second stage, using think-out-loud protocols. In the current study we specifically focus on the first stage. A first look at the already existing literature around challenge-based education and modular instruction shows us that both concepts have been around for a long time in higher engineering education. Since education has become more and more digitized (and the development of MOOCs), it appears that the concepts have taken a quick increase in relevance. However, both concepts have only been studied minimally in relation to each other. We deem it thus highly relevant to first build a clear and proper view on both concepts, the strengths and weaknesses, and where both (can) meet. So that anyone who has intentions like ours - to implement both in higher education - can do this in an evidence-informed manner.

¹ *Corresponding Author*

C Mesutoğlu

c.mesutoglu@tue.nl

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, part of a project is presented that aims at presenting a framework to design challenge-based, modular education courses in engineering education. Merks et al. [1] have described a course redesign focused on making a course challenge-based and modular at Eindhoven University of Technology. In order to help teachers within that and other universities to redesign their courses as well, or in other words, to scale up the work done by Merks et al. [1], an evidence-based framework for challenge-based and modular education is essential. The project (CMODE-up) consists of three stages: (1) the development of a preliminary set of design principles for challenge-based modular education, resulting from (1a) informal interviews with key actors at our university, experienced in studying and/or designing modular instruction, (1b) a systematic literature review on challenge-based education and modular education instruction; (2) the development of the CMODE-up framework after a test of the previously developed design principles; and (3) a test of the CMODE-up framework, that was built on the results from the second stage, using think-out-loud protocols. This paper specifically focuses on stage 1 (both a and b).

Modular education or modularization as a concept, has been around in higher education since Harvard University initiated an elective course system in the late 1800s [2]. Accordingly, the set curriculum was replaced and the students were given the freedom to decide and take courses in the program that matched their learning needs. Since then, many educationalists have adapted a modular perspective to education, but throughout time, modular education has taken different meanings; e.g. many studies refer to modularization as it was first used at Harvard University, other studies mean that within a course different modules can be defined and students go through these modules in chronological order, or they even choose themselves what modules they take and in which order [2]. The latter type, where the modules are independent of each other and nonsequential, can be considered the most ideal type of modularization, since it offers students the autonomy and flexibility to follow the modules as a mix and match program, while still ending up with regular certification [3]. Following a modular course structure, students achieve success in multiple course modules as well as create connections between these modules [4]. Key features in all these perspectives on modularization are flexibility, frequent feedback, self-paced learning and adaptations to individual students' needs [5]. For CMODE-up, we are interested in modular course structures, regardless of whether the modules are independent and nonsequential. In research, the modular perspective to course design has its roots in learning theories such as programmed instruction, and student-centered pedagogies [6, 7].

1.1 Modular course design

The higher education literature presents design and development of modular course structures. An example course design focused on maker education. The researchers required some of the modules to be mandatory but also left the rest of the

modules to be chosen by the students upon their interests and learning needs [8]. Another course was developed with a modular approach for mechatronics engineering students. The course modules combined theoretical knowledge and learning activities for the students to apply what they learn as they create solutions to the design challenges at hand [9]. In line with the framework of challenge-based learning (CBL), several educational modules were designed that included course learning outcomes and the learning experiences. The modules were designed to facilitate mastery of the content and the skills that the students would need to finalize the challenge [9]. The CMODE framework by Merks et al. [1] is another example of the movement towards modular education for higher engineering education. In this redesign, a traditional course was restructured into several theory modules, centered around a challenge that was also ‘modularized’ into deliverables accompanying the theory modules. Testing this redesign showed that dividing a single CBL course into modules with specific learning outcomes and learning activities can lead to positive student learning outcomes.

To take on a modular approach to course design, multiple aspects in higher education need to be considered: a) the educational program to be modularized, b) the students and their background (e.g., prior knowledge, needs, interests), c) teacher preparedness, d) learning and instruction, and e) organizational support [2]. Given the lack of an empirically-grounded framework targeting higher engineering education, the iterative development of a framework can provide a valid structure for designing courses with a modular approach. This study aims to present design principles to be used in an evidence-based framework for modular course design.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Stage 1a: Informal interviews

Interviews were conducted with 13 professionals who have experience with modular instruction in higher engineering education contexts at Eindhoven University of Technology. All interviewees were contacted using personal networks. The interview questions addressed interviewees’ experiences in designing modular courses for higher engineering education. The interviews questions include: “1) What are your experiences in modular instruction in relation to higher engineering education? and 2) In what ways is modularity extending CBL and higher engineering education further?” The researchers’ field notes are used during data analysis [10].

The researchers carefully read the fields notes taken during the interviews several times. As a result of a descriptive analysis [10], general categories were created to summarize the findings.

2.2 Stage 1b: Systematic Literature Review

Content analysis method was adopted to conduct the systematic literature review [10]. Multiple searches were conducted in the databases: Ebsco, Web of science, Scopus.

The keywords used to locate the articles included: “engineering education”, “challenge-based learning”, “modules”, “modular courses”, and “content modules”. These keywords were used in different combinations to locate as many appropriate articles as possible. The search was limited to articles published in peer-reviewed journals between 2000 and 2021. Books, book chapters and conference proceedings were not included in the search. The removal of duplicates decreased the located number of articles from 545 to 486. Of the 486 unique articles, titles and abstracts were studied using exclusion criteria: a) studies that do not target higher engineering education, b) publications such as commentaries, reports, short documents, c) studies not written in English, and finally d) studies that either report modules as software or device (e.g., protein module, solar module, modular simulators) or discuss modular approach only in their recommendations. If one of these exclusion criteria was applicable to an article, the article was excluded from further analysis. Application of these criteria decreased the total number of articles to 201. A further examination was later completed using inclusion criteria. Only the articles that at least one of the two criteria applied to were included: a) explained modularization of a course, curriculum, or a program in a higher engineering education context and b) described how the modules were created.

Later in this stage, the authors individually examined the retained 103 articles using codebooks. The codebooks included the themes and the codes based on their total occurrences found in the data. Use of codebooks facilitated the organization of the review findings [10].

3. RESULTS

3.1 Stage 1a

The informal interviews have provided an overview of what higher engineering education and modular education look like at Eindhoven University of Technology, at the moment. Table 1 provides an overview of the range of practices and perspectives at TU/e regarding these concepts. From the interviews it already appeared that even if a university like TU/e has a vision to have more challenge-based and modular courses, design of such courses differs a lot, depending on the perspective the course designer has on these concepts.

3.2 Stage 1b

Using two codebooks, the authors coded all articles included in the systematic literature review. Frequencies and the percentages have been calculated for all themes and codes. The first codebook illustrated the descriptive characteristics of the articles; year, location, engineering discipline, classification of module (e.g., learning module, instructional module), sources for module design, and teacher contribution. The frequencies were calculated separately for articles that reported on modules in programs, and for articles that reported on modules to be integrated in courses. The second codebook included the design aspects to create modules for higher engineering education courses. The identified codes included learning outcomes, student feedback,

self-pacing-status, focus of modules, delivery of modules, pedagogical framework, and instructional sources.

Table 1. Categories that surfaced in the interviews

Categories	Description
Higher engineering education context	Challenge-based, design-based course contexts
Structures that resemble modularity	Structures that lie somewhere between traditional courses and modular courses, the course is not entirely modular but students are highly encouraged to personalize the instruction and learning by other means
Degree of modularity	The variety in modular course structure; the courses allow multiple degrees of sequence, flexibility, choice and individualized instruction for the students
Characteristics	The benefits and limitations of modular courses for higher engineering education
Instructional principles	Conceptual background; how the course is structured (e.g., steps followed, interdisciplinarity, alignment to the design challenge, assessments)
Computer-assisted learning	The value and role of digital platforms in modular course structures
Roles	The roles of teachers and students in a modular course structure
Teachers	Teacher preparedness and the importance of teacher professional development
Organizational aspects	The institutional vision towards modularity in higher engineering education, existing and planned support

4. NEXT STEPS

Completion of Stage 1a and Stage 1b resulted in a set of design principles, that in Stage 2 are being tested with five professionals and teachers within Eindhoven University of Technology in order to come up with the initial version of a framework for instructional design for challenge-based modular education. In its current form, the set of design principles are represented with two documents: 1) 10 instructional design steps and 2) a brief teacher manual with the best practice articles identified from the literature to represent each design step. Later, in Stage 3, the initial version of the framework will be validated with think-aloud interviews. The think-out-loud tasks will be based on the initial version of the framework and on helpful sources on cognitive interviewing, higher engineering education and modular course design [5, 11].

REFERENCES

[1]	Merks, R., Stollman, S., & Lopez Arteaga, I. (2020). Challenge-based modular on-demand digital education: A pilot. <i>Presented at SEFI Conference, 20–24 September.</i>
[2]	Dochy, F. J. R. C., Wagemans, L. J. J. M., & de Wolf, H. C. (1989). <i>Modularization and student learning in modular instruction in relation with prior knowledge.</i> Netherlands: Centre for Educational Technological Innovation.
[3]	Dejene, W., & Chen, D. (2019). The practice of modularized curriculum in higher education institution: Active learning and continuous assessment in focus. <i>Cogent Education</i> , Vol. 6, No. 1, 1–16.
[4]	Boahin, P., & Hofman, W. A. (2014). Perceived effects of competency-based training on the acquisition of professional skills. <i>International Journal of Educational Development</i> , Vol. 36, 81–89. doi:10.1016/j.ijedudev.2013.11.003
[5]	French, S. (2015). <i>The benefits and challenges of modular higher education curricula.</i> Melbourne: Melbourne Centre for the Study of Higher Education.
[6]	Dewey, J. (1986). <i>Experience and education.</i> New York, NY: Kappa Delta Pi.
[7]	Jaehrig, W., & Miller, M. L. (2007). Feedback types in programmed instruction: A systematic review. <i>The Psychological Record</i> , Vol. 57, No. 2, 219–232.
[8]	Cohen, J., Gaul, C., Huprich, J., & Martin, L. (2019). Design and development of a modular maker education course for diverse education students. Presented at the <i>Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference (SITE)</i> , San Diego, California.
[9]	Félix-Herrán, L. C., Rendon-Nava, A. E., & Jalil, J. M. N. (2019). Challenge-based learning: An I-semester for experiential learning in mechatronics engineering. <i>International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)</i> , Vol. 13, No. 4, 1367–1383.
[10]	Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2012). <i>How to design and evaluate research in education</i> (8th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Companies.
[11]	Botma, Y., Van Rensburg, G. H., Coetzee, I. M., & Heyns, T. (2015). A conceptual framework for educational design at modular level to promote transfer of learning. <i>Innovations in Education and Teaching International</i> , Vol. 52, No. 5, 499–509.